

New pairs of acyl sucroses from *Petunia nyctaginiflora* Juss.

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Four new acyl sucroses, isolated from *Petunia nyctaginiflora* Juss. (Solanaceae) were characterised as 2,3,4-trihexanoyl- α -D-glucopyranosyl- β -D-fructofuranoside, 2,3,4-triheptanoyl- α -D-glucopyranosyl- β -D-fructofuranoside, 2,3,4-trihexanoyl- α -D-glucopyranosyl- β -D-6-acetyl fructofuranoside, 2,3,4-triheptanoyl- α -D-glucopyranosyl- β -D-6-acetyl fructofuranoside, on the basis of chemical and spectroscopic evidence.

In continuation of our recent reports of the isolation and characterization of four new acyl sucroses^{1,2}, from the epigeal part of *Petunia nyctaginiflora* Juss. (Solanaceae), we describe herein, the isolation, purification and structure determination of another two pairs of acyl sucroses from the same source. The chemical investigation was based on the significant biological importance of acyl sucroses³⁻⁶.

Results and discussion

The *n*-hexane extract of the epigeal part of *Petunia nyctaginiflora* was partitioned with aqueous methanol (80%) and the aqueous methanol layer was concentrated and chromatographed over a bed of silica gel to yield two compounds, designated as PNC and PND. Benzene : ethylacetate (4 : 6) eluate yielded PNC and benzene : ethylacetate (6 : 4) eluate yielded PND. PNC and PND were found to be similar to each other, except the presence of acetate methyl group (δ_{H} 2.12, 3H, s) in PND, which was absent in PNC.

IR spectrum of PNC showed broad bands at 3600 and 3510 cm^{-1} and a strong absorption band at 1745 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of hydroxyl and ester carbonyl groups in the sample. ^1H NMR spectrum of PNC showed signals for a number of oxymethylene and oxymethine hydrogens between δ 3.50 and 5.60 including a proton doublet at δ 5.65 (J 3.5 Hz) might be due to an anomeric hydrogen of sugar molecule. Spectrum also showed signals at δ 1.25 attributed to a number of acyl moieties, along with triplet from δ 2.20 to 2.50 might be due to ketomethylene and it was thus assumed that the signals were associated with a long chain acyl function.

Acetylation of PNC with acetic anhydride and pyridine, at room temperature yielded pentaacetyl derivative of PNC. The IR spectrum of which did not show any band in the hydroxyl region, indicating acylable nature of five hydroxyl groups present in PNC. ^1H NMR spectra of PNC acetate showed signals for five acetate groups at δ 2.17 (6H), 2.12 (3H), 2.11 (3H) and 2.10 (3H). The signals for one anomeric hydrogen and of a number of oxymethylene and oxymethine in the ^1H NMR spectrum of PNC and its acetate derivative indicated them to be a sugar derivative.

Basic hydrolysis of PNC, after subsequent work-up gave an oily liquid, presumably a mixture of fatty acids, from the less polar fraction and a sugar from the polar fraction. The sugar was identified as sucrose $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{11}$, m.p. 184°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} +66.1^\circ$ (H_2O); octaacetate, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_{19}$, m.p. 87–89°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} +58.5^\circ$ ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) by direct comparison with authentic sample of sucrose and its octaacetyl derivative. The isolation of sucrose by alkali hydrolysis of PNC with formation of pentaacetate derivative, taken in conjunction with the observed hydroxyl and ester bands in the IR spectrum of the compound suggest that PNC is a sucrose molecule with three of its eight hydroxyl groups remaining as esters. This assumption was confirmed from an analysis of 500 MHz ^1H NMR spectrum of PNC, which showed the anomeric hydrogen signal at δ 5.65 (1H, J 3.5 Hz) and three oxymethine hydrogen signals at a relatively lower field at δ 4.95, 5.16 and 5.55. Thus, the three acyl functions of PNC in the pyranose ring, occupying three contiguous position, was verified by an analysis of H-H COSY spectrum, which showed connectivity of the anomeric hydrogen at δ 5.65 with the low-field carbinyl hydrogen at δ 4.94, which in turn showed connectivity

with the carbinyl hydrogen signal at δ 5.55. Again, the carbinyl hydrogen signal at δ 5.55 was flanked between the hydrogens showing signals at 4.94 and δ 5.16.

To ascertain the nature of acyl function, PNC was subjected to trans esterification with sodium methoxide in methanol to yield methyl esters. GLC analysis of which showed it to be a mixture of methyl ester of different fatty acids, and these ester functions were placed at C-2, C-3 and C-4 position of the pyranose ring that may be same or different. The purity of PNC was checked by HPLC analysis of its benzoate derivative, prepared by benzylation with benzoyl chloride and pyridine and was found to be a mixture of several compounds of close elution time. Purification of PNC benzoate was achieved by use of reverse phase silica column (RP-18) and methanol as eluent. The fractions of PNC corresponding to peaks showing retention time 12.8 and 15.9 min were collected separately and labeled as PNC benzoate I and PNC benzoate II.

PNC benzoate I, ($C_{65}H_{72}O_{19}$) showed a distinct ester carbonyl band at 1740 cm^{-1} in its IR spectrum. Alkali hydrolysis of PNC benzoate I, yielded sucrose and the mixture of two acids, which on treatment with *p*-bromophenacyl bromide and Et_3N , followed by separation of the mixture by HPLC yielded *p*-bromophenacyl benzoate and an ester of *p*-bromophenacyl hexanoic acid. The latter compound was characterised from comprehensive spectral analysis. The structure of PNC benzoate I was settled as **1** and its natural product PNC I as **2**.

Similarly, alkali hydrolysis of PNC benzoate II, ($C_{68}H_{78}O_{19}$) yielded sucrose and a mixture of acids, treatment of which with *p*-bromophenacyl bromide and Et_3N followed by separation using HPLC yielded, in addition to the expected *p*-bromophenacyl benzoate, *p*-bromophenacyl ester of heptanoic acid. The latter compound was characterized from comprehensive spectral analysis. Thus, PNC benzoate II was expressed as **3** and its natural product PNC II as **4**.

Well dried sample of PND showed in its IR spectrum, broad bands at 3600 and 3510 cm^{-1} and a strong absorption band at 1745 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of hydroxyl and ester carbonyl groups in the sample. Like its congener PNC, the 1H NMR spectrum of PND showed signals for a number of oxymethylene and oxymethine hydrogens between δ 3.50 and 5.60 and signal for an anomeric hydrogen (δ 5.65, J 3.5 Hz) of sugar molecule. In addition the spectrum showed a signal for an acetoxy group at δ 2.1 (3H, s) along with signals for methylene ketomethylenes and methyl groups which may be attri-

- 1 $R = C_5H_{11}$, $R_1 = R_2 = COC_6H_5$
- 2 $R = C_5H_{11}$, $R_1 = R_2 = H$
- 3 $R = C_6H_{13}$, $R_1 = R_2 = COC_6H_5$
- 4 $R = C_6H_{13}$, $R_1 = R_2 = H$
- 5 $R = C_5H_{11}$, $R_1 = COC_6H_5$; $R_2 = COCH_3$
- 6 $R = C_5H_{11}$, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = COCH_3$
- 7 $R = C_6H_{13}$, $R_1 = COC_6H_5$; $R_2 = COCH_3$
- 8 $R = C_6H_{13}$, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = COCH_3$

Fig. 1

buted to long chain acyl function.

Acetylation of PND with Ac_2O and pyridine, at room temperature yielded tetraacetyl derivative of PND, the IR spectrum of which was devoid of any band in the hydroxyl region indicating acylable nature of the hydroxyl group in the PND. 1H NMR spectra of PND tetraacetate showed signals for altogether five acetate groups at δ 2.17 (6H), 2.12 (3H), 2.11 (3H), 2.10 (3H), suggested that the four hydroxyl groups in PND are acylable in nature. A comparison of 1H NMR (500 MHz) spectrum of PND tetraacetate and PNC pentaacetate established the identity of both the compounds. It is therefore inferred that PND is a monoacetyl derivative of PNC.

Since the 1H NMR spectrum of PND showed signals for only three carbinyl hydrogen in downfield region therefore it was considered that the acetate ester was present either at C-6 position of glucopyranose ring or at C-1' or C-6' position of fructofuranose ring of sucrose molecule. C-1' position was excluded because the signals associated to these hydrogens δ 3.60 (2H, dd) in PND, moved downfield by 0.5 ppm (4.10, 2H, q). A careful examination of 1H NMR spectrum of PNC, showed that the signals for two $-CH_2O-$ group are at δ 4.30 and 3.79 (2H each), which may be attributed for C-6- H_2 and/or C-6'- H_2 . This problem was solved by careful analysis of H-H COSY spectrum of PND, which showed that the signals for C-6- H_2 hydrogens appeared at δ 3.74 and 3.84 (1H, dd each). The spectrum showed signals for C-6- H_2 and

C-6'-H₂ centered at δ 3.79 and 4.30 respectively. Therefore it became clear from the chemical shift (δ 4.30) of C-6'-H₂ that the acetate group in PND must be present at C-6' position.

Like its congener PNC, PND benzoates prepared by benzylation with benzoyl chloride and pyridine, also showed in HPLC chromatogram, a mixture of several compounds of close elution time. Purification of PND benzoate was achieved by use of reverse phase silica column (RP-18) with methanol as eluent. The fractions of PND benzoate corresponding to peaks showing retention time 15.0 and 19.0 min were collected separately and labeled as PND benzoate I and PND benzoate II.

PND benzoate I, (C₆₀H₇₀O₁₉) was obtained as waxy solid and it showed a distinct ester carbonyl band at 1740 cm⁻¹ in its IR spectrum. Alkali hydrolysis of PND benzoate I, afforded sucrose and the mixture of two acids, which on treatment with *p*-bromophenacyl bromide and Et₃N and separation of the mixture by HPLC yielded *p*-bromophenacyl benzoate and an ester identified as *p*-bromophenacyl ester of hexanoic acid from comprehensive spectral analysis. The structure of PND benzoate I, was settled as **5** and its natural product PND I as **6**.

Similarly, alkali hydrolysis of PND benzoate II, (C₆₃H₇₆O₁₉), yielded sucrose and a mixture of acids, treatment of which with *p*-bromophenacyl bromide and Et₃N yielded, in addition to the expected *p*-bromophenacyl benzoate, *p*-bromophenacyl ester of heptanoic acid. The latter compound was fully characterized from comprehensive spectral analysis. Thus, the structure of PND benzoate II was formulated as **7** and the corresponding natural product PND II as **8**.

Experimental

General :

Melting points were obtained on a Yazawa hot stage microscope and uncorrected. IR spectra on a JASCO-IR 180 spectrometer in CHCl₃ solution. ¹H NMR were recorded on JEOL 270 MHz or JEOL GSX-500 spectrometer using CDCl₃ solution with tetramethylsilane as internal reference. Mass spectra were measured on JEOL JMX-SX, direct inlet system. HPLC was carried out using reverse phase (ODS) Shim-pack column and UV detector.

Plant material :

The epigeal part of *Petunia nyctaginiflora* Juss. were collected from the campus of Banaras Hindu University,

Varanasi, India. A specimen of the plant material has been preserved in the Department of Medicinal Chemistry, IMS, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India.

Extraction and isolation :

Air dried epigeal parts of *Petunia nyctaginiflora* (5 kg) were milled and soxhletted with *n*-hexane. The *n*-hexane extract was concentrated (2.5 l) and partitioned with equal volume of MeOH : H₂O (1 : 4) mixture. The aqueous methanol soluble portion obtained was evaporated under reduced pressure to a residue (19.5 g) which was chromatographed over silica gel column and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. Benzene-ethyl acetate (4 : 6) eluates yielded PNC (7 g) and benzene-ethyl acetate (6 : 4) eluates yielded PND (10 g). PNC : γ_{\max} 3600, 3510 and 1745 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.65 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, anomeric-H), 5.62 (1H, m, -CHOR), 5.15 (1H, m, -CHOR), 4.96 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2 and 3.9 Hz, -CHOR), 4.20 (4H, m), 3.79 (2H, m), 3.45 (4H, m, 2 × -CH₂OH), 2.30 (m, -COCH₂, -COCH), 1.25 (br s, methylenes), 0.88 (methyls). PND : γ_{\max} 3600, 3510 and 1745 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.65 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, anomeric-H), 5.55 (1H, m, -CHOR), 5.16 (1H, m, -CHOR), 4.94 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2 and 3.9 Hz, -CHOR), 4.25 (7H, br m, 3 × -CHOH, 2 × -CH₂OH), 3.94 (1H, m, -CHO), 3.60 (2H, dd, *J* 12.2 Hz), 2.30 (m, -COCH₂), 2.12 (3H, s, OAc), 1.25 (br, methylene), 0.88 (3H, t, CH₃).

Acetylation of PNC to PNC acetate :

A mixture of PNC (0.2 g), Ac₂O (1 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml) was kept overnight under anhydrous condition at room temperature. The reaction mixture after usual work up yielded PNA pentaacetate (0.22 g) as a gummy residue. δ_{H} 5.92 (3H, m), 5.22 (1H, dd, *J* 3.5 Hz, anomeric-H), 5.17 (1H, m), 4.86 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2 and 3.9 Hz), 4.30 (6H, m), 4.15 (5H, m), 2.07, 2.17 (6H, s, 2 × -OAc), 2.12 (3H, s, 1 × -OAc), 2.11 (3H, s, 1 × -OAc), 2.10 (3H, s, 1 × -OAc), 1.22 (br s, methylenes), 1.08 (d, methyl), 0.85 (m, methyls).

Basic hydrolysis of PNC :

A solution of PNC (0.10 g) in 10 ml of 5% methanolic KOH was refluxed for 1 h. Basic solution was cooled, neutralized carefully with 2 *N* HCl and diluted with water (10 ml), and resultant solution was extracted with Et₂O (3 × 10 ml), methanol was evaporated under reduced pressure, the solution was then extracted with *n*-BuOH. Butanol soluble portion was evaporated to dryness and divided into two parts. Part I was crystallised from aqueous alcohol to colourless cubes, C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁, m.p. 183–

185°, $[\alpha]_D +66.1^\circ$ (H₂O). Part II was treated with Ac₂O/pyridine at room temperature for 24 h. After usual work-up the reaction mixture yielded sucrose octaacetate m.p. 87–89°, $[\alpha]_D +58.5^\circ$, δ_H 5.61 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz, anomeric-H), 5.38 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, -CHOAc), 5.37 (1H, t, *J* 10 Hz, -CHOAc), 5.30 (1H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, -CHOAc), 5.00 (1H, t, *J* 10 Hz, -CHOAc), 4.80 (1H, dd, *J* 10.0 and 4.0 Hz, -CHOAc), 4.04–4.30 (8H, m, 3 × -CH₂OAc, 2 × -CHO), 2.01–2.05 (18H, s, 6 × -OCOCH₃), 1.94 (3H, s, -OCOCH₃), 1.92 (3H, s, -OCOCH₃).

Benzoylation of PNC :

A mixture of PNC (0.2 g), benzoylchloride (2 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml) was kept overnight under anhydrous condition. The reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice, stirred for 0.5 h and extracted with CHCl₃, washed, dried, freed from pyridine *in vacuo* and chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with *n*-hexane-ethyl acetate (8 : 2), yielded PNC benzoate.

Isolation of PNC benzoate I (1) and PNC benzoate II (3) :

PNC benzoate (0.21 g) was dissolved in methanol (0.2 ml) and was purified by reverse phase Shim-pack silica gel (RP-18) column. The detector used was UV 254 nm, chart speed 10 mm/min and flow rate was 6 ml/min with methanol as eluent. HPLC chromatogram showed two prominent peaks corresponding to 12.5 to 13.2 min and 15.6 to 16.2 min which were collected separately and designated as PNC benzoate I and PNC benzoate II respectively, the solvent was removed under pressure.

PNC benzoate I (1) :

C₆₅H₇₂O₁₉, δ_H 8.04 (10H, m), 7.45 (15H, m), 6.0 (1H, d), 5.92 (1H, m), 5.85 (1H, d), 5.58 (1H, m), 5.15 (1H, m), 4.95 (1H, dd), 4.74 (1H, m), 4.63 (3H, m), 4.36 (1H, dd), 4.08 (2H, br), 2.15 (t), 2.47 (6H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 1.68 (6H, q), 1.29 (12H, q), 0.76 (9H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz).

PNC benzoate II (3) :

C₆₈H₇₈O₁₉, δ_H 8.05 (10H, m), 7.45 (15H, m), 6.01 (1H, d), 5.92 (1H, m), 5.55 (1H, m), 5.16 (1H, m), 4.93 (1H, dd), 4.63 (3H, m), 4.36 (1H, dd), 4.07 (2H, br), 2.4 (6H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 1.68 (6H, q), 1.29 (18H, br m), 0.76 (9H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz).

Basic hydrolysis of PNC benzoate I (1) :

Basic hydrolysis of PNC benzoate I (30 mg) was carried out as described in case of PNC. Sugar part was identified as sucrose, C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁, m.p. 184–185°. The Et₂O soluble part was evaporated and dried to give acid mixture (6 mg).

p-Bromophenacyl esters of acid mixture :

Acetonic solution of acid mixture (5 mg) obtained from the basic hydrolysis of 1, was added to a solution of *p*-bromophenacyl bromide (0.15 g) and triethylamine (0.2 ml) in 5 ml of acetone, the resultant mixture was stirred on an oil bath for 0.25 h at 50°. The acetone was evaporated under N₂ stream and the residue was passed through a silica gel column and eluted with ether. The eluates were combined and concentrated under reduced pressure giving a mixture of *p*-bromophenacyl ester of acids. Preparative HPLC of *p*-bromophenacyl ester was done and two peaks with elution time 5.3 and 7.1 min respectively were obtained. The fraction corresponding to peak with elution time 5.3 min, after evaporation of the solvent yielded a residue (5 mg), was identified as *p*-bromophenacyl benzoate, C₁₅H₁₁BrO₃; *m/z* 318/320 (M⁺), 196/198, 183/185, 155/157, 105, 77, 51, 50. Evaporation of the solvent from fraction corresponding to peak with elution time 7.1 min, yielded a residue (1.8 mg), which was characterized as *p*-bromophenacyl ester of hexanoic acid, C₁₄H₁₇BrO₃; γ_{\max} 3030, 2960, 2930, 2060, 1742, 1703, 1595, 1422, 1400, 1375, 1230, 1182, 1110, 1075, 1050, 925, 820 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.77 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.63 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 5.28 (2H, s, ArCOCH₂), 2.47 (2H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz, 2-H₂), 1.68 (2H, q, *J* 7.4 Hz, 3-H₂), 1.55 (1H, m, CH), 1.29 (4H, m, 2 × -CH₂), 0.76 (3H, t, -CH₃); *m/z* 326/328 (M⁺), 312/314, 256/258, 196/198, 183/185, 169/171, 155/157, 113, 57, 43, 29.

Basic hydrolysis of PNC benzoate II (3) :

The same procedure was obtained for the basic hydrolysis of PNC benzoate II (28 mg), which produced sugar part, which was identified as sucrose C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁, m.p. 184–185° while the Et₂O soluble portion was evaporated and dried to give acid mixture (6.1 mg). The *p*-bromophenacyl ester of acid mixture was prepared and purified by preparative HPLC as done in case of PNC benzoate I (1). The fraction corresponding to retention time 5.3 and 7.9 min, respectively were collected separately. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The eluate corresponding to retention time 5.3 min was identified as *p*-bromophenacyl benzoate, C₁₅H₁₁BrO₃; *m/z* 318/320 (M⁺), 196/198, 183/185, 155/157, 105, 77, 51, 50. The eluate corresponding to retention time 7.9 min, was characterized as *p*-bromophenacyl ester of heptanoic acid C₁₅H₁₉BrO₃, δ_H 7.77 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.63 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 5.28 (2H, s, ArCOCH₂), 2.47 (2H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz, 2-H₂), 1.68 (2H, q, *J* 7.4 Hz, 3-H₂), 1.36 (2H, m), 1.22 (4H, br), 0.75 (3H, t);

m/z 326/328 (M^+), 256/258, 198/200, 183/185, 169/171, 155/157, 143, 127, 69, 55, 41, 29.

Acetylation of PND to PND acetate :

A mixture of PND (0.1 g), Ac_2O (1 ml) and pyridine (0.4 ml) was kept over night under anhydrous condition at room temperature. The reaction mixture after usual work-up yielded PND tetraacetate (0.11 g) as gummy residue.

Basic hydrolysis of PND :

A solution of PND (0.06 g) in 10 ml of 5% methanolic KOH was refluxed for 1 h. Basic solution was cooled, neutralized carefully with 2 *N* HCl and diluted with water (10 ml), and resultant solution was extracted with Et_2O (3×10 ml), methanol was evaporated under reduced pressure and the resultant solution was then extracted with *n*-BuOH. Butanol soluble portion was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was divided in two parts. Part I was crystallized from aqueous alcohol to colourless cubes; $C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$; m.p. 183–185°, $[\alpha]_D +66.1$ (H_2O). Part II was left overnight with Ac_2O /pyridine at room temperature for 24 h. The reaction mixture after usual work up yielded sucrose octaacetate $C_{28}H_{38}O_{19}$; m.p. 88°; $[\alpha]_D +58.5^\circ$ (C_2H_5OH).

Benzoylation of PND :

A mixture of PND (0.5 g), benzoyl chloride (5 ml) and pyridine (0.2 ml) was kept for 12 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice, stirred for 0.5 h and extracted with $CHCl_3$, washed, dried, freed from pyridine *in vacuo* and chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with *n*-hexane-ethyl acetate (8 : 2) yielded PND benzoate (0.60 g).

Isolation of PND benzoate I (5) and PND benzoate II (7) :

PND benzoate (0.2 g) was dissolved in methanol (2 ml) and was purified by chromatography over reverse phase Shim-pack silica gel (RP-18) column. The detector used was UV 254 nm, chart speed 10 mm/min and flow rate was 6 ml/min with methanol as eluent. HPLC chromatogram showed two prominent peaks, the eluents corresponding to retention time 14.8 to 15.5 min and 17.1 to 17.6 min were collected separately and designated as PND benzoate I (5) and PND benzoate II (6) respectively, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure.

PND benzoate I :

$C_{60}H_{70}O_{19}$; δ_H 8.04 (10H, m), 7.45 (15H, m), 6.0 (1H, d), 5.92 (1H, m), 5.85 (1H, d), 5.58 (1H, m), 5.15

(1H, m), 4.95 (1H, dd), 4.74 (1H, m), 4.63 (3H, m), 4.36 (1H, dd), 4.08 (2H, br), 2.47 (6H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 1.68 (6H, q), 1.29 (12H, br m), 0.76 (9H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz).

PND benzoate II (7) :

$C_{63}H_{76}O_{19}$; δ_H 8.05 (10H, m), 7.45 (15H, m), 6.01 (1H, d), 5.92 (1H, m), 5.85 (1H, m), 5.16 (1H, m), 4.93 (1H, dd), 4.63 (3H, m), 4.36 (1H, dd), 4.07 (2H, br), 2.47 (6H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 1.68 (6H, q), 1.29 (18H, br m), 0.76 (9H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz).

Basic hydrolysis of PND benzoate I (5) :

Basic hydrolysis of PND benzoate I was carried out as described in case of PND. Sugar part was identified as sucrose, $C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$, m.p. 184–185°, while the Et_2O soluble portion was evaporated and dried to give acid mixture. *p*-Bromophenacyl ester of acid mixture was prepared as described earlier. Preparative HPLC of *p*-bromophenacyl ester derivative of acid mixture was done and the eluents corresponding to two peaks with retention time 5.3 and 7.1 min were collected. The fraction corresponding to retention time 5.3 min after evaporation of the solvent yielded a residue (7 mg), which was identified as *p*-bromophenacyl benzoate, $C_{15}H_{11}BrO_3$; m/z 318/320 (M^+), 196/198, 183/185, 155/157, 107, 77, 51, 50. Evaporation of the solvent from fraction corresponding to retention time 7.1 min yielded a residue (2 mg) which was characterized as *p*-bromophenacyl ester of hexanoic acid $C_{14}H_{17}BrO_3$.

Basic hydrolysis of PND benzoate II (7) :

The same procedure was followed for the basic hydrolysis of PND benzoate II, as in case of PND benzoate I. The sugar part was identified as sucrose $C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$, m.p. 184–185° while the Et_2O soluble portion was evaporated and dried to give acid mixture. The *p*-bromophenacyl ester of acid mixture were prepared and purified by preparative HPLC as done in case of 5. The fraction corresponding to retention time 5.3 min was collected separately and identified as *p*-bromophenacyl benzoate, $C_{15}H_{11}BrO_3$; m/z 318/320 (M^+), 196/198, 183/185, 155/157, 105, 77, 51, 50. The eluate corresponding to retention time 7.9 min was characterized as *p*-bromophenacyl ester of heptanoic acid $C_{15}H_{19}BrO_3$.

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